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An innovative approach to reduce burden of stress among women teachers

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Abstract

Stress is unavoidable part of life due to increasing workload and complexities of life. Now-a- days the world is said to be the world of achievement side by side the world of stress. Stress is anywhere and everywhere amidst family, friends, business, institute or society. At present situation women are enjoying varied roles within the family and within the work place. Women suffer in each side from mental tension and physical harassment at workplaces in addition to the common job stress. The most important recommendations of the study included setting up a clear and particular strategy for developing educational evaluations, the development of educational work in line with technological developments, and employing self-evaluation methods. The main focus of this study is to analyse the practices of innovative stress management at the work place among the school female teacher. This study has been applied to explore their psychological and physiological response see able of their profession as a tutor.

Keywords: Teacher stress, Work Pressure, Humanized management, social support

Introduction

Work-related stress is one of the important, prevalent issues among the researchers in the modern educational sciences as well as the organizational behaviour. The occupational stress is indeed one of the major problems incurred by public and private organization's staff, leading to institutional and entrepreneurial unproductive power and lower institutional quality and profitability.

Nearly all people experience some sort of stress. Human pressures and stresses lead to worry and anxiety, which have adverse effects on psychological and physical health both at home or in normal life. On the other hand, work-related stress is increasingly recognized as one of the most serious occupational health hazards, reducing workers' satisfaction and productivity and increasing absenteeism and turnover.

The work should be dealt with in a narrower range of pressures. Job stress is an embedded part of work, besides members of staff are usually exposed to different levels of occupational stress, especially in the educational arena. The educators are often exposed to situations that exceed their responsibilities and abilities.

Many researchers argue that workers' reactions and their unwanted behaviour, such as increased absenteeism and turnover, frequent complaints, increasing occupational faults, poor performance and other related forms of behaviour, are caused by stress at work due to heavy workload and multiple relationships, which eventually lead to unbearable stress and burnout. Recent research has attempted to find solutions for the mental work-related issues in order to ensure smooth flow of work and prevent any unnecessary administrative problems, which probably arise from inadequate psychological surroundings.

There is a major trend to addressing the work-related stress in educational institutions since teachers constitute the largest group of the teaching workforce. Indeed, the teacher is the most important element in the educational process and the cornerstone in the process of the professional development. He is directly responsible for the achievement of the educational targets, and he is the most influential person in his students' behaviours. In addition, he plays other significant roles, including the development of leaders and workers in various fields and

disciplines as well as the delivery of knowledge, education, and noble values in the minds of his students.

Teaching is the most important profession of all because it provides the society with the academically and socially, technically and morally qualified human resources. However, it is one of the most stressful jobs that leads to psychological and physical pressures because it is a very demanding job.

The study shows that there are two main sources of work-related stress. It comes from the nature of the work environment and the workmates, including stress from the physical environment, as well as individual, social, and organizational factors. The second source constitutes the individual's intellectual and emotional features as well as his capacities and needs. According to Gray and Starke, work-related stress is the combination of reactions that result from a combination of situations in the surroundings. They lead to a set of psychological and physiological variables on the individual. Likewise, Al-Abdali refers to seven major sources; six are internal, and one is external. These include work, role organization, stages of growth, environmental and climate regulations, internal relationships in the environmental regulations, higher regulations, and personality components. Many of the studies confirm the correlation between stress and performance where increasing stress levels lead to poorer performance. Most business organizations tend to believe that stress at work has adverse effects on their performance. On the other hand, it has indeed some desirable effects. Kelly argues that it motivates the individual towards excellence and achievement of his objectives as he believes it constitutes the essence of his existence.

The Negative Effects of Job Stress are Divided into Many Types

- **The effects of stress at workplace:** Work-related stress has many implications, such as low levels of quality and productivity, accident-prone concentration, inconvenient working atmosphere, low morale, lack of job satisfaction, poor employee interrelations and unacceptable behaviour, higher turnover, lateness and absenteeism; and long-term illnesses.
- **Psychological effects:** job stress affects the employees' psychological status, often leading to depression, anxiety and occupational accidents.
- **Behavioural effects:** increasing pressure at work often leads to bad habits such as smoking, weight loss, sleep disorder, hostility, and apparent lack of respect for institutional guidelines and regulations.

The researcher concludes that the positive effects of stress at work are scarce compared with negative effects, which cause lower productivity, poor employee interrelations, along with poor socialization with family and friends and unhealthy relationships in the social contexts.

Therefore, the issue of stress work is very significant for the teachers in particular due to the Palestinian community's social, political and economic conditions, which have huge implications for the society as a whole. Besides, it leads to despondent circumstances for the members of the community who work in different domains.

Research Methodology

Research design proposed for the study is descriptive type of research. This type of research deals with quality of responses from the respondents regarding their attitudes, interests, technical skill, experience and self-concept etc.

Source of data

The source of data for this research is an absolutely primary data.

Primary

Primary data was collected through questionnaire survey method among the female teachers in private schools at India. The primary data were collected from 110 respondents for school teachers.

Secondary

The secondary data were collected from the Newspaper, Journals, Magazines, books and unpublished dissertation.

Sample size

In this study simple Descriptive sampling of purposive was used to select 110 female teachers as the study respondents. This is because in view of the researchers, the respondents possess particular pieces of information that the researchers would need for the study as regards to workplace stress and its management. There researchers therefore, selected private school female teacher in India for the study.

Occupational stress

The work stress factors relating to the school teachers in the inadequate training. Staff shortage and work over time are the predominant factors. The various reasons for stress factors have been presented as below table.

Table 1: Occupational Stress

S. No.	Variables	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total	Mean
1.	Given supportive feedback on the work	94	8	5	2	1	110	4.7455
		9	1.8	4.5	7.3	85.5	100	
2.	Have work very intensively	11	88	8	2	1	110	3.9636
		10.0	80.0	7.3	1.8	9	100	
3.	To maintain discipline and order in class room	85	9	11	4	3.6	110	4.5727
		77.3	8.2	10.0	3.6	9	100	
4.	Total working hours per day	20	43	39	6	2	110	3.6636
		18.2	39.1	35.5	5.5	1.8	100	
5.	Time limit cover the syllabus and conduct test or not	75	15	12	3	5	110	4.3818
		68.2	13.6	10.9	2.7	4.5	100	
6.	Regular check up by higher officers	26	52	27	5	0	110	3.9000
		23.6	47.3	24.5	4.5	0	100	
7.	Level of academic achievement of students	73	12	22	3	0	110	4.4091
		66.4	10.9	20.0	2.7	0	100	
8.	How often do you feels stressed	29	27	46	7	1	110	3.690
		26.4	24.5	41.8	6.4	0.9	100	

It is clear from the table that the highest level of 77.3% of the respondents strongly agree and 80.0% agree with respondents are very interested in the job. The respondent's involvement in the job shows 80% of the respondents agree and 52% of the respondents agree with the time limit to cover the syllabus and conduct test or not. About 52% of the

respondents agree with the respondents are proud in the job and 50% of the respondents agree with the job in the organization is challenging. However, the highest of 8.2% disagree and 14.05% strongly disagree with the respondents are really very proud of their jobs in the organization. The average acceptance score reveals that the job is a very interesting is one of the most important factors (4.5727) for the respondent’s school teachers, followed the job gives them better status in the organization (4.4091). However,

with regard to the job of everyone in this organization is challenging the respondents assign least acceptance.

Problem Faced by Female School Teachers

The female teacher faced selection problem lack of high-level qualification, lack of professional, teaching training and government negligence regarding female teacher teachers working too many roles at the same time.

Table 2: Problem faced by female school teachers

S. No.	Variables	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total	Mean
1.	Heavy work load	82	16	8	3	1	110	4.5909
		74.5	14.5	7.3	2.7	0.9	100	
2.	Pressured to work long hours	23	74	8	4	1	110	4.0364
		20.9	67.3	7.3	3.6	0.9	100	
3.	Frustration	72	20	10	7	1	110	4.4091
		65.5	18.2	9.1	6.4	0.9	100	
4.	Work load of the teacher is too heavy	27	51	28	3	1	110	3.9091
		24.5	46.4	25.5	2.7	0.9	100	
5.	Many problems working in rural areas	65	22	19	3	1	110	4.3364
		59.1	20.0	17.3	2.7	0.9	100	
6.	Financial problem at home	45	39	19	5	2	110	4.0909
		40.9	35.5	17.3	4.5	1.8	100	
7.	Stress due to technological problem	52	30	23	5	0	110	4.1727
		47.3	27.3	20.9	4.5	0	100	
8.	Think physical environment problem in the work place causes stress	54	30	20	6	0	110	4.2000
		49.1	27.3	18.2	5.5	0	100	
9.	Low salary	57	19	29	3	2	110	4.2273

It evident from the table 5.01 the teachers the strongly agree and 74.5% of the respondent’s Heavy work load and agree with the 67.3% of the pressured to work long hours are important reason for work stress among the school teachers however they disagree 6.4% of the frustration. And strongly disagree 1.8 low salary important reason for work stress among the Indian school teachers the majority of the mean value 4.5909.

Different Stress Management Activities & Results

There are many stress management techniques to try including physical mental, social, intellectual and environment techniques. Some of these include yoga, healthy eating, exercise, massage, meditation, and stress management activities.

Table 3: Stress management activities

S. No.	Variables	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total	Mean
1.	Class room management	99	7	3	1	0	110	4.854
		90.0	6.4	2.7	0.9	0	100	
2.	Flexibility of working time	13	78	17	2	0	110	3.9273
		11.8	70.9	15.5	1.8	0	100	
3.	Clear expected at work	72	18	16	4	0	110	4.4364
		65.5	16.4	14.5	3.6	0	100	
4.	To supervise students during breaks	25	29	50	6	0	110	3.6636
		22.7	26.4	45.5	5.5	0	100	
5.	Group discussion to students	60	26	20	2	2	110	4.2727
		54.5	23.6	18.2	1.8	1.8	100	
6.	Clarity of information	25	37	40	7	1	110	3.7091
		22.7	33.6	36.4	6.4	0.9	100	
7.	Short time frame for making question paper	53	29	25	3	0	110	4.2000
		48.2	26.4	22.7	2.7	0	100	
8.	Social activities	31	31	39	7	2	110	3.7455
		28.2	28.2	35.5	6.4	1.8	100	
9.	Teaching students with special learning needs	72	24	11	2	1	110	4.4909
		65.5	21.8	10.0	1.8	0.9	100	
10.	Achievement of target on time	34	44	27	4	1	110	3.9636

Out of total 70.09% of the respondents agree with the increase morale in the school teacher and 40% of the teachers the standard of living in the school teachers towards the respondents.33.6%, 23.6% and 16.4% of the respondents agree with the clarity of information, clear expected at work & group discussion to students is respectively.

About 40% agree with the increase achievement of target on time. Out of total 90% of the respondents strongly agree with the towards class room management. The mean score indicates the 4.49 of the respondents in the teaching students with special learning needs.

Data Analysis

Regression analysis

Hierarchical multiple regression was used to determine whether coping strategies moderate relationship between teacher stress and social support. For each model, stress and coping strategies were controlled.

Table 4: The percentage of different five pressure ratings on subscales of TSQ

Pressure ratings	Social stress (%)	Occupational stress (%)	Personal stress (%)
No influence	30.7	21.5	47.2
Mild influence	28.1	26.7	29.0
Moderate influence	21.0	24.0	15.1
Severe influence	12.3	17.1	6.3
Extremely severe influence	8.1	10.9	2.4

To have an overall understanding of teacher stress, we calculated the percentage of different five pressure ratings (no influence, mild influence, moderate influence, severe influence, extremely severe influence) on subscales of TSQ. We found that only 30.7, 21.5 and 47.2 per cent of the participants reported that they suffer no influence from social stress, occupational stress and personal stress, respectively. However, more than half of the teachers felt under from mild to extremely severe stress, especially, they experienced high level of occupational stress. Detailed descriptive information is presented in Table 4.

Table 5: Means and standard deviations of descriptive variables on subscales of TOSQ

Stress	Vocational (n=224)	Regular (n=139)	Male (n=75)	Female (n=239)	Under 40 (n=146)	More than 40 (n=59)	Less 10 Years (n=90)	Over 10 Years (n=116)
Social stress	1.68 ± 0.61	2.28 ± 0.80	1.67 ± 0.71	1.89 ± 0.71	2.06 ± 0.72	1.97 ± 0.66		2.07 ± 0.71
School stress	2.59 ± 1.00	2.86 ± 1.03	2.48 ± 1.04	2.66 ± 1.01	2.87 ± 1.05	2.79 ± 0.94	2.71 ± 0.96	2.96 ± 1.05
Personal stress	1.77 ± 0.66	2.04 ± 0.81	1.73 ± 0.72	1.85 ± 0.70	1.99 ± 0.71	1.73 ± 0.66		1.88 ± 0.70
Total stress	2.01 ± 0.65	2.40 ± 0.75	1.96 ± 0.72	2.14 ± 0.68	2.30 ± 0.68	2.16 ± 0.62		2.30 ± 0.69

Additional descriptive information about means and standard deviations of different gender, age, type of teacher (vocational teacher or regular teacher) and years of teaching (less than 10 years or over 10 years) on subscales of TSQ are presented in Table 5.

Conclusion

From the above study, researcher has concluded that the stress among the teachers is common and existing everywhere. Though the respondents are having good supportive feedback mechanism regarding class room management and relationship, sometime they find it difficult to practice it. So, teachers should be allowed to participate in trainings, social services and other stress management related programme in the school. Working environment (regular or vocational schools), gender and age affect teacher stress. Social support and passive strategies have significant relationships with teacher stress, and passive strategies play a moderating in the relationship between social support and teacher stress. This study demonstrates that more social support should be provided by educational administrators, and teachers should be trained to avoid using passive strategies to reduce teacher stress.

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